

Can a music game improve motor coordination in children with cerebral palsy? A feasibility study

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Abstract— This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of a music game, in combination with physiotherapy, in improving motor coordination in children with cerebral palsy. A pilot study was conducted with children diagnosed with cerebral palsy, aged 7-18 years, who received conventional physiotherapy along with the Moniz Game. Motor coordination was assessed using the Nine-Hole Peg Test and the Manual Tapping Test at baseline and after the intervention. The Moniz game sessions lasted 15 minutes and were conducted twice a week for 6 weeks. Improvements in motor coordination were observed in both the Nine-Hole Peg Test and Manual Tapping Test at the final assessment. However, these improvements were not statistically significant. The combination of conventional physiotherapy with the Moniz Game shows potential as an effective tool for enhancing motor coordination in children with cerebral palsy. While the results were not statistically significant, the intervention appears feasible and warrants further investigation with a larger sample size.

Keywords — cerebral palsy, serious games, music, motor rehabilitation

I. INTRODUCTION

Cerebral palsy can be defined as a non-progressive impairment that occurs in a developing brain [1] with a prevalence of approximately 3 per 1000 births[2]. The signs and symptoms vary in each case; however, in the majority of cases, children experience complications in motor skills, affecting both the upper and lower limbs [3].

Physiotherapy is essential for developing motor abilities that promote independence and improve the quality of life

for these individuals [3], [4],[5]. Therapy should have clear objectives and incorporate playful elements to engage children in the treatment process[6].

One strategy to keep pediatric patients engaged is the gamification of the therapeutic process [7]. This involves integrating games and reward or ranking elements to motivate children to perform physiotherapy activities [8], [9], [10].

The integration of technology into physiotherapy, particularly through gamification, represents a growing trend in pediatric rehabilitation. By combining entertainment and structured therapy, it becomes possible to address the unique challenges faced by children with cerebral palsy in an innovative and interactive manner. Moreover, such approaches may pave the way for further advancements in personalized and motivating treatment strategies for this population [11], [12], [13].

The Moniz Game is a music-based game developed to simulate music training on mobile devices. The objective of the game is for players to reproduce musical sequences proposed by the game. The system's usability was evaluated by physiotherapists, receiving a global score of 88.65 [14], which is classified as "Best Imaginable."

In this study, we aim to evaluate the effectiveness of the Moniz Game in improving the motor coordination of children with cerebral palsy. The findings will contribute to understanding how gamified tools can enhance therapeutic engagement and outcomes.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Study Design and Sample

This is a pilot study assessing the feasibility of a complementary intervention for physiotherapy using a within-subjects study design. A convenience sample was used. All procedures took place at the Polyclinic of Mogi das Cruzes in 2023. The inclusion criteria were: diagnosis of cerebral palsy, age between 3 and 18 years, and regular attendance at the pediatric neurological physiotherapy clinic. Exclusion criteria included cognitive deficits that hindered understanding of the tasks proposed by the project, hearing impairments, or upper limb deformities.

B. Ethical Aspects

After approval by the Ethics Committee of the University of Mogi das Cruzes (protocol number: 58975422.8.0000.5497), the process of volunteer selection began. Children and their legal guardians who agreed to participate in the research signed the Free and Informed Consent Form.

C. Motor Coordination Assessment

To evaluate motor coordination, two tests were conducted: the Nine-Hole Peg Test and the Manual Tapping Test.

In the Nine-Hole Peg Test, the participant was seated in a chair with back support, in front of a desk with the test platform. The platform consisted of two compartments: one for storing pegs and another for inserting them. The therapist explained the procedure to the participant, who was instructed to take the pegs one by one from the storage compartment and insert them into the other compartment. After all the pegs were inserted, the participant then removed them one by one and placed them back in the storage compartment. The time taken to complete the task was recorded, and the test was performed bilaterally (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Nine Hole Peg Test

In the Manual Tapping Test, the setup and position were similar to the Nine-Hole Peg Test. The desk featured

two circles and a rectangle. The participant placed the non-dominant hand in the rectangle while using the dominant hand to tap alternately between the two circles as quickly as possible, completing 25 cycles (Figure 2). The time taken was recorded, and the test was also performed bilaterally.

Fig. 2. Manual Tapping Test

D. Interventions

During the study, all participants continued their regular physiotherapy sessions at the clinic. The intervention with the music game (Moniz Game) was conducted after the conventional treatment. The children were seated in front of a desk with a Samsung tablet (model A8, Android operating system). Participants were instructed to perform the game tasks using both hands and to try to engage all their fingers. The game included levels of increasing difficulty, each featuring distinct melodies that had to be reproduced accurately to complete the challenge. Participants interacted with the game for approximately 15 minutes per session (Figure 3).

E. Procedures

The study lasted for 10 weeks. In the first four weeks, all participants underwent only conventional physiotherapy, with no exposure to the music game. During this phase, motor coordination was assessed in weeks one and four.

In the second phase, combining conventional physiotherapy and the music game (weeks 5 to 10), participants were introduced to the music game with a frequency of two sessions per week. Motor coordination assessments were conducted in weeks 7 and 10 (Figure 4).

Fig. 3. Moniz Game Interface

Fig. 4. Procedures

F. Statistical Analyses

The normality of the data was verified using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Comparisons between assessments were performed using the Friedman test. Additional analyses were conducted using median and interquartile range (IQR). The statistical tests were carried out using SPSS software version 28 and BioEstat 5.0.

III. RESULTS

Eight volunteers were recruited at the beginning of the study. However, one did not attend any sessions, and two missed the motor coordination assessments; therefore, their data could not be included in the analyses. The remaining five participants had a mean age of 12.4 years (range: 7–18 years, ± 5.42). Among them, two were boys and three were girls (40% and 60%, respectively). All participants exhibited more pronounced impairments in the left upper limb. When

analyzed by median and IQR, it was observed that after six weeks of physiotherapy interventions combined with the music game, all metrics showed improved scores in the final week compared to previous assessments (Figure 5).

In the assessment of the Nine-Hole Peg Test for the right hand (Table 1), a trend of increased time to complete the task was observed. However, in the final week, there was a reduction compared to the third assessment. The Friedman test revealed no significant differences between the evaluations ($\chi^2 = 2.52$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.472$), indicating that the observed changes in performance were not statistically significant.

TABLE 1. Nine Hole Peg Test – Right Side (Seconds)

Evaluation	1	2	3	4
Median	42.00	46.03	49.05	45.05
IQR	8.93	4.95	12.05	10.99
First Quartile	36.09	42.07	38.03	40.02
Third Quartile	45.02	47.02	50.08	51.01

In the assessment of the Nine-Hole Peg Test for the left hand (Table 2), an oscillation in the improvement of time was observed. In the final week, the score was lower than in the first week, indicating that participants required less time to complete the task successfully. The Friedman test revealed no significant differences between the evaluations ($\chi^2 = 1.56$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.668$), suggesting that the changes in performance were not statistically significant.

Fig. 5. Box Plots of Nine Hole Peg Test and Tapping Manual Test

TABLE 2. Nine Hole Peg Test – Left Side (Seconds)

Evaluation	1	2	3	4
Median	46.01	45.05	52.01	41.08
IQR	24.02	30.96	37.29	45.06
First Quartile	45.04	43.08	43.01	39.02
Third Quartile	69.06	74.04	80.30	84.08

TABLE 4. Manual Tapping Test – Left Side (Seconds)

Evaluation	1	2	3	4
Median	48	38	40	36
IQR	7	12	12	11
First Quartile	43	35	31	28
Third Quartile	50	47	43	39

In the Manual Tapping Test for the right hand, an oscillation in performance was observed between weeks 2 and 3. However, the time in the final week was the best among all the assessments. Statistical analysis using the Friedman test revealed no significant differences in performance across the four evaluations ($\chi^2 = 3$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.373$) (Table 3). This suggests that the changes observed in the median scores and variability were not statistically significant. In the Manual Tapping Test for the left hand, a trend of decreasing time was observed week by week, with the best time, similar to the right hand, recorded in the final week of assessment. The Friedman test indicated no significant differences across evaluations ($\chi^2 = 7.08$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.069$), suggesting that the observed changes were not statistically significant (Table 4).

TABLE 3. Manual Tapping Test - Right Side (Seconds)

Evaluation	1	2	3	4
Median	35	32	35	26
IQR	19	23	14	14
First Quartile	28	22	29	25
Third Quartile	47	45	43	39

IV. DISCUSSION

In this study, we aimed to verify whether a music game, when associated with physiotherapy, could be more effective in improving motor coordination in children with cerebral palsy. The Moniz Game was briefly assessed by physiotherapists, and we confirmed that the system is tangible and feasible for use with the target population. Despite motor impairments, all participants were able to manipulate the game and interact as expected.

The use of games with musical elements is gaining traction in the literature. For example, Dauvergne created a rhythm game on a tablet for patients with Parkinson's disease, which was used in a home setting [15]. The results regarding acceptability and usability were positive, and all participants showed improvement in their rhythmic skills. While there are possibilities for improving both the game and the intervention methodology, systems like the Moniz Game, which use a tablet interface, offer a different training strategy for motor outcomes.

In both the Nine-Hole Peg Test and the Manual Tapping Test, improvements were observed in the final assessments of participants. However, these improvements were not statistically significant. We hypothesize that with a larger sample, the results could have been more expressive.

Nevertheless, the findings suggest that a music game on a tablet requires at least 3-4 weeks to show measurable improvements in motor coordination in children with cerebral palsy [16], [17], [18], [19].

The 15-minute interaction time with the music game was considered satisfactory and appropriate for children, as it allows for progressive interaction without being too long to induce monotony or loss of curiosity [20], [21], [22].

This study has some limitations. The first limitation is the small sample size, which may have prevented the data from being fully representative. The second limitation was the challenge of administering the motor coordination tests. Often, children were not fully engaged in performing the tests, and we believe that their motivation to participate directly affected the magnitude of the results [23], [24].

CONCLUSION

Conventional physiotherapy, when combined with a music game (Moniz Game) on a tablet, has the potential to be a new tool for improving motor coordination in children with cerebral palsy. Interventions may need to last at least 3-4 weeks to observe improvements. While improvements in motor coordination were observed, the results were not statistically significant.

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